

Strategic Planning of Public relations - Reducing uncertainty in Decision making

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Abstract

Nowadays, corporate communication can't be fully understood without the contribution of public relations. Publics are fundamental for all corporations and ways to communicate with them have gained new challenges, products and solutions due to social changes and ICT technologies available and furthermore due to new needs from different publics. For this reason, the desired level of action improvement in each project should be calculated to arrive at the best set of cost / outcome measures. As the actions are implemented and the results measured it can be said that the Public Relations Plan is continuously recycled All this leads corporate communication to evolve to a more careful, wide and accurate strategic planning.

IJSB

Accepted 18 November 2019
Published 19 November 2019
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3547481

Keywords: Communication, Corporate Communication, Public Relations, Publics, Strategic Planning, ICT.

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Introduction

"The public can go to hell!!" These words, uttered by US railroad mogul William Vanderbilt in 1873, determined the birth of public relations and allowed the consolidation of the new power of public opinion, for so many years ignored. Whitaker Pentead (1993), supported by Edward Bernays' narration, describes the episode: Vanderbilt, the colossus of the US railroads at the time, orders traffic to close at a small extension, which continually had negative results. The users, without means of transportation to their workplaces, react non conformally, leading to demonstrations and clashes with the police. New York newspapers follow events, and *The Times* (at the time, a small independent newspaper) highlights a novice journalist whose mission, to the delight of veteran colleagues - aware of the difficulty of the task - is to get an exclusive interview with the powerful William Vanderbilt; the impossible happens, and the novice gets the longed for interview. The meeting takes place in a tumultuous manner, and when urged to respond to the measures he intended to take to re-establish traffic, which is essential for the displaced working-class population, the irascible President of the Railway exalts, shouting: "The public can go to hell!" In the newsroom, this is the phrase chosen for the headline of the newspaper edition. And the small, unimpressive *The Times* catches the eye of New Yorkers, whose eagerness to search compels successive editions. Public opinion, hitherto unable to speak, and subject to the large media that depended on the interests of the powerful, merely publishing what was convenient, reacts and refuses to "go to hell." Over the course of weeks, the newspaper goes deeper into the subject, denouncing this and other excesses, so common at the time, and rampant corruption in business and government. As a result, and about a month after the *Times* headline, Vanderbilt himself publishes a denial of the controversial interview on the front pages of all US newspapers, and takes a moderating stance, afraid of the new power of public opinion.

Public relations is really born at this point: when companies start showing respect for the public, which has always been ignored (Fawkes, J., 2018). Mckie & Sriramesh present a very important summary about Public Relations:

Public relations is better described than defined. It is an applied professional practice and an academic field, and both offer communication centered and research based ways to understand, inform, and intervene to adjust relationships between ideas, individuals, groups, and societies. The practice seeks to influence the building, maintenance, and restoration (or, on occasion, destruction) of reputations and also to integrate different perspectives and groups, particularly through its enactment of activities such as issues management, crisis resolution, and risk communication. Because the field's major arena of social action is the public sphere, especially in media (online and offline), politics, and public opinion, public relations activities can impact significantly on democracy. Public relations practitioners have, for example, helped mobilize populations to participate, or cease participating, in wars. Individuals and organizations who use public relations range from CEOs, corporations, governments (local and national), and think-tanks through to activists, charities, educational institutions, health organizations, NGOs, and ordinary people. (2017, p. 1)

It is therefore essential, within the framework of an approach on the subject of the public of the institutions, to resort to the fundamental concept of public opinion. The fundamental question is its definition: for Wilcox [et al] (1992: 234), "Public opinion is the sum of individual opinions on an issue affecting those individuals", or "Public opinion is the collective

expression of opinion of many individuals". bound into a group by common goals, aspirations, needs, and ideals. "(idem, ibidem). How do you graduate? According to Lendrevie [et al] (2010; 1990: 364), it results from "various forms of communication that come to us from different parts and which eventually allow us to express value judgments about certain facts or events." In the words of Broom (2009 [1985]: 216), "Public opinion has never been more powerful, more fragmented, more volatile, and more exploited and manipulated".

Public opinion is thus a dynamic force, so part of the mission of communications technicians will be to help organizations recognize, understand and deal with this powerful influence on their internal and external environments. It reflects a continuous process of interpersonal and mediated communication on certain topics between groups of people who have the faculty to act in a similar way. "Thinking together" often leads to "acting together", which makes it particularly important to understand this phenomenon, which obliges more and more institutions to publicize their activities and promote them in order to get a favorable average of the opinions of individuals and groups. It is therefore up to the communication professional, the task of studying and interpreting the opinions of the publics on which he will carry out his activities. It is important to work on the opinions of these groups, which are of direct interest to the institution's activities, through persuasive and adapted communications (Broom, 2009 [1985]). counterproductive, as in any society it is possible to find a mosaic of different ethnic, religious, geographical, social, political and occupational to target audiences (Bueno, 2003, 2007).

It is necessary to know each audience specifically and in detail in order to be able to understand them, set goals, develop effective communication strategies and evaluate their results. Selecting the most effective ways an organization can communicate with its audiences is crucial. If these were a homogeneous whole, the task of communicating with them would certainly be made easier, but certainly less stimulating. What actually happens is that audiences are complex, distinct groups whose interests do not always coincide. For the communication technician, knowledge of this audience dynamics is essential. "A successful campaign must be aimed at those segments of the mass audience which are most desirable for its particular purpose and must employ those media most effective in reaching them." (Wilcox [et al], 1992: 262).

Thus, we see that any institution, whether pursuing social or non-profit objectives, has diverse audiences and has to manage relationships with each. Given the scope of Public Relations, it is essential that the organization proceeds with a generic segmentation at two levels: internal and external audiences, although institutions often forget or invest little of their time and budgets in actions aimed at internal publics. Theoretically, however - and from an antagonistic perspective to the one referred to above - when identifying the various targets of an organization, it is common to create an ordering according to the degree of proximity. internal publics. Equally noteworthy is the relevance normally given to the media because they convey information that leads other human groups to form opinions. For this reason, organizations that pay particular attention to you are frequent, for example by creating the specific position of Press Officer that is now responsible for the difficult task to integrate ICT and recent technologies in Public Relations, as Mylona & Amatanidis tell us:

The impact of the internet on how we lead our lives today in the developed countries can be seen in our everyday activities. Communication process has been affected as

traditional ways of communications seems to be used less as time is passes. Internet, social media, mobile phone, SMS are new ways of communications that has been adopted and used in the western world. Technology seems to play an important role the ways that public relations are exercised. Public relations practitioners in international originations and companies understood the importance of social media. It is beneficial for public relations practitioners to understand how to use these tools as they relate to their jobs. A recent study by Parveen et al (2015) investigates the various purposes of social media usage and its impact on organizational performance focuses only on the social media managers' views. The results also show that social media has a greater impact on the performance of organizations in terms of enhancement in customer relations and customer service activities, improvement in information accessibility and cost reduction in terms of marketing and customer service. Also social media is highly used is to develop a good relationship with customers, to have effective communication with customers. Social media tools help organizations to have two-way communication with customers and has helped to improve the performance of the organizations in various areas. (2017, p. 1 – 2)

We can then, and as Dewey advocates (apud Broom, (2009 [1985]: 219), define an audience as “an active social unit consisting of all those affected who recognize a common problem for which they can seek common solutions.”) Whitaker Penteado (1993: 45) defines audiences as “the group of people in which PR work develops.” For Kotler and Armstrong, (2007 [1993]: 48), “audiences are any group that has a real interest or potential or impacting the company's ability to achieve its objectives. ”These authors propose the following categorization of audiences: Financial audiences - all those that influence the organization's ability to raise funds, such as banks or shareholders; Media audiences (Radio, Television or Press) - disseminate news about various events related to the institution; Government audiences - central and local authorities; Interest groups - groups that, acting in a variety of fields, can put pressure on the organization to act in either direction. Examples: consumer organizations, environmental groups, minority representatives ...; Local audiences - who share a particular geographic location with the organization: community institutions, commerce, service sector ...; General public - groups all people who have some level of interest for the institution in some way related to its products and activities; Internal Audience - Includes volunteer technicians, senior and senior management, for whom some specific communication media can be used to inform and motivate. Penteado, in turn, proposes that it be used - while referring to the subjectivity inherent in the human sciences, and the consequent difficulty in establishing absolute truths - the criterion of proximity, that is, the one that gives primacy to the public closest to the organization. Thus, the author systematizes (1993): Internal audiences of an institution: Company Owners, Shareholders, Employees, Community, Resellers; External audiences of an institution: Suppliers, Consumers, Competitors, Representative employers, Professional unions, Information agencies, Government, General public.

Equally noteworthy, in presenting some variations, is Jacques Lendrevie [et al] (2010 [1990]) view of the specific audiences of an institution according to proximity criteria, and in descending order of importance: Shareholders, Directors , Workers (all of which are considered the internal audiences of the organization.), Consumers / Users, Distributors, Prescribers, Suppliers, Opinion Leaders, Financial Community, Trade Unions, Employers

Associations, Local Community, Central and Local Government, Media, Public in General (external audiences).

To conclude the theme, and as stated by Penteado (1993: 33): "Public opinion is sovereign. Difficult as it is to detect and know, it is where public relations efforts should be directed. In this sense we can understand Edward Bernays' definition: "Human Engineering". Public Relations is effectively a form of human engineering because it builds on the public's opinion the basis of the success of any enterprise." In this way, and even more important than the specific criterion used, it seems to us to be careful that the message is conveyed in the right sense, that is, adapted to the target audience, so it is essential to locate it. For such, it is necessary to determine the audiences and define their priority scales adjusted to each specific institution.

Public Relations: functions and instruments, roles and tools

We then saw how slowly public relations has been gaining credibility and crucial importance for the success of organizations. The need to equip those who perform it with the right knowledge and tools has become urgent as it takes on an increasingly diverse and active role in the pursuit of the management objectives of organizations. This professional activity contributes, in complex societies such as the one in which we live, to the mutual understanding between the groups, and the consequent harmony of their different policies, serving various types of institutions, such as companies, unions, power agencies, associations, foundations, hospitals, schools or churches. To achieve their goals, these structures develop relationships with their audiences whose attitudes and values they need to understand. The public relations professional therefore acts as a mediator, who transforms particular goals into policies and actions aimed at the common good (Capriotti, (2008 [1999])). For Lendrevie [et al] (2010; 1990), Public Relations assumes as its primary objectives the following: to gain notoriety for the organization and endow it with credibility with its publics; make known and justify its positioning, highlighting its contributions to the well-being of the community; obtain goodwill from the power agencies and attract investors; face in delicate situations; achieve internal and external humanization of the organization, for example through the creation in employees of feelings of belonging and sharing values.

For Viegas Soares and Costa Pereira (1997), the main functions that delimit the field of activity of Public Relations are: daily reading and analysis of Social Communication, as well as the establishment of communications with the media; conducting surveys or studies that report the opinion of internal and external audiences to the company; thorough knowledge of the company's strategy, its mission and objectives, in order to properly disclose it. According to Fonseca (1998), supported by the propositions of the Public Relations Society of America, the functions that delimit the work of a Public Relations professional are as follows: Planning and developing communication programs in accordance with the general policies of the organization; Reconcile relationships between an entity and its various audiences; Research the opinions and attitudes of the internal and external audiences of the organization, and use the instruments necessary to modify them, if appropriate; Analyze the impact of the implementation of organizational policies on the various audiences; Proceed, whenever appropriate, to adjust and correct these organizational policies, while keeping in mind the public interest and the survival of the organization; Advise managers in their decisions regarding the establishment of new policies; Establish and maintain two-way communication between the organization and all its audiences. The author also adds the need, on a

permanent basis of a true policy, to engage the public in order to achieve an organizational climate of good understanding, open to dialogue and change. Regarding this theme, however, the perspective of Penteadó (1993) seems to us to be extremely pertinent and coherent, when he states that they constitute Public Relations simultaneously: (1) a management philosophy, as they translate a set of notions general, symbol of the conception of business life. As a guiding principle, it argues that any organization is a public servant, and deserves reward in proportion as it contributes to the common good. Its main objective should therefore be to improve the living conditions of its public, as they will reward those who do so; (2) a management function, since it is undeniably useful for Public Relations to be able to predict market conditions, to organize the content of communications bridging individuals, to direct the organization with the consideration that others deserve, for easily integrate into working groups, coordinate the institution from within and also in its external relations, and monitor to monitor the life of the company and make changes as necessary; (3) a communication technique, for the ability to fill the empty spaces that modern life has left open between publics and institutions. If in the past these communications were direct and there was reciprocal knowledge between the parties involved, the fact is that progress and today's complex life have destroyed these relationships, with impersonality and complete ignorance between sellers and buyers, or even between managers and leaders. employees. Public Relations has the capacity to fill these gaps, humanizing modern economic activities; (4) a system of human behavior, in the sense that, within an organization, all employees practice public relations in the various daily acts, as their attitudes exert enormous influence on their image.

Following these findings, and recognizing the reductive character of any attempt to systematize the functions of Public Relations, the author proposes the consideration of a broad objective: the attunement of interests, in order to accurately adjust the conveniences of organizations and all those who relate to it internally or externally. It is from this line that the institution can extract the conditions for its development, so it is also the function of excellence of the Public Relations professional. For Wilcox [et al] (1992: 7-9) "public relations often play a dual role. On one level, they serve as advisers and counselors to management. On another level, they often function as technicians using a tool bag of communication techniques (...) to tell the public about management actions and decisions. " These authors state that, among others, Public Relations professionals perform the following tasks: Advise the Administration on the policies to be adopted; Planning public relations programs; Achieve the cooperation of all employees in the projects of the organization; Speaking or writing speeches for others; Plan and conduct meetings; Arranging press conferences; Contact with the media; Plan public opinion polls; Plan and organize events; Arrange for the publication of leaflets, pamphlets, reports and bulletins; Edit internal publications; Prepare film making and multimedia presentations; Plan and organize fairs; Photograph or ensure the presence of photographers on justified occasions; Evaluate public relations programs; Conduct fundraising campaigns; Plan and manage crisis communication programs. Regarding Communication Crisis, ICT and actual Social Media, Eriksson wrote about advices for effective social media crisis communication given by researchers in various subdisciplines of strategic communication and focused on 5 issues:

Effective social media crisis communication is about: (1) exploiting social media's potential to create dialogue and to choose the right message, source and timing; (2) performing precrisis work and developing an understanding of the social media

logic; (3) using social media monitoring; (4) continuing to prioritize traditional media in crisis situations; and finally, (5) just using social media in strategic crisis communication. These guidelines mainly emerged from quantitative research conducted in the context of the United States and on Twitter. There is need for more research focusing on other platforms and other empirical material. There is also a future need for an in-depth methodological discussion of how to further bridge the gap between research and practice on a global scale, and how to develop more evidence-based recommendations for strategic crisis communication practitioners (2018, p. 1)

We believe that by describing the roles that Public Relations can perform, it will be easier to understand their field, or the wide range of activities and objectives related to this practice. Similarly, we think we can identify the building and maintenance of mutually beneficial relationships essential to modern societies as the moral and ethical basis of the profession. As far as applicable modes and instrumentation are concerned, and being, by definition, an instrument "any agent employed to perform a work is all that serves as a means to an end." (Penteado, 1993: 69), We believe it is indispensable, in a work of this nature, to examine the main modes and respective specific instruments of Public Relations, and, of course, some of them will be more or exclusively suited to the internal audiences, and others to the external audiences of the organization:

1. Events

An institution can increase its visibility through events that attract the favorable attention of its target audiences. For example, they could sponsor academic conferences, highlight important occasions in the life of the organization to which invitations are made, organize days of visits to media facilities, or family and friends of staff - often referred to as Open Days or Open Days - support, through sponsorship or sponsorship, the organization of cultural or sporting / recreational events, or organize exhibitions and fairs. Each well-conducted event impresses attendees and provides the basis for media-driven news (Costa, 2003 [2001]).

2. Institutional Identity Stands

Occasionally this type of material comes up with different visual, graphic or chromatic characteristics, a situation that creates confusion in the minds of those who receive the messages; Moreover, an opportunity to create or reinforce institutional identity is overlooked. In an overinformed society, organizations have to compete for attention, and one of the most effective ways to do this is to try to create a visual identity that the public recognizes immediately. This visual identity, of which the central element is the logo, appears on the institution's permanent media, such as house-organs, booklets, brochures, flyers, posters, notice boards, welcome manuals, forms, business cards and uniforms, and becomes a great marketing tool when it's attractive, memorable and unique. The task of creating this visual identity is not easy, it first involves identifying the essence of the institution, and then turning it into a great idea, supported by strong visual symbols (Dilenschneider, 2000).

3, Public Service Activities

In modern Western societies, it is increasingly important to take action with a socially responsible bent, such as protecting the environment, animal and plant species, or defending social causes. The advancement of ideas, the development of the media, or the increase in the level of literacy, make modern man more sensitive to these issues related to the increase in quality of life. Thus, actions that reveal a concern on the part of organizations, will tend to generate positive impressions in their audiences (Costa, (2003 [2001]; Dilenschneider, 2000).

Unlike the previous ones, the public relations instruments listed below are applicable in a specific crisis communication context, although they also have the “everyday” utility that we attribute to them below. Its applicability in contexts of tension we will deal with later, in its own chapter dedicated to the central theme of our thesis.

4. News

The Public Relations department is also tasked with drafting news about the institution and disseminating it through the appropriate media in the apparent form of news. This written advertising has some qualities that make it a worthwhile investment: firstly, it gets more trust from recipients than advertising, as it appears in their eyes as “normal” news, not information Paid. Secondly, its high drama potential, as news of a remarkable event catches the eye. This is also likely to be what are probably the best known PR tools: the Press Release, the Press Dossier and the Press Conference. A competent public relations technician also knows that the media is looking for interesting, up-to-date news, and that institutions must compete in terms of attention with all the other news of the day. It will therefore be very useful to know as many editors and journalists as possible to provide the Press Releases. But even more so, the Public Relations Department must also respond promptly and courteously to media contacts requesting interviews (Fortes, 2003; Gillis, 2011).

5. Speeches

The Head of Public Relations should also look for managers and heads with above-average oratory skills, who may represent the institution at appropriate opportunities.

6. Personal contact

It is never too much to mention the fact that the managers and leaders of an organization are its face to external audiences. However, other people directly related to it also play the role of Public Relations: employees, former employees, shareholders and volunteers. The impressions they convey have a significant impact on how the institution is perceived by third parties, hence the need for them to be made aware of this. Also of note is the importance of setting up clubs (cultural, sports ...) and the organized reception and integration of new workers.

7. Audiovisuals

Instruments such as films or internal television circuits have relevant use as communication tools in organizations. Sensorially appealing, they facilitate message retention by its recipients.

8. Multimedia

With technological developments and the advent of the Internet, new forms of communication have emerged, such as e-mail, video conferencing, electronic newsletters, corporate blogs or wiki technology, as reported by Alves and Scorsolini-Comin (2012). Fortes (2003: 242) states: “The computerized propagation of data and information has given rise to a new enriched perspective of understanding and adjustment among people, groups and companies: virtual communication. Nowadays, the citizens who dedicate themselves to the virtual means of communication are emerging, which will open unprecedented possibilities of relationship, if the company revises its normal processes of distributing information to its audiences.”

In this scenario also appears the intranet, an important vehicle of internal communication today, which has advantages over traditional instruments. Peretti (cited Remondes (2011) “clearly states that the concept of intranet evolves into an internal collaboration platform in the future.” In fact, with the huge exponential increase in Internet use, it was not long before individuals recognize that components that worked so well on the Internet could be equally

valuable within organizations and that is why intranets have become so popular. For Nielsen (2000) and Palmerston [et al.] (sd), The great advantages presented by internal networks have sparked a revolution in corporate communication. Reducing costs, distancing interlocutors, increasing productivity and creating new possibilities for institutional interaction have all come true. The network supports work routines, enables the communication of employees from different sectors, obtaining the necessary information to work, as well as reducing the The circulation of paper also adds that there is a great concern with the design of intranets, because if it is pleasant can communicate the spirit and corporate attitude to all employees. Thus, intranets that are concerned with usability achieve efficiency and satisfaction of the institution's employees. Cibys [et al.] (2010) systematize that usability aims to develop simple, intuitive and easy-to-use interfaces, as these qualities allow users to feel confident and satisfied to achieve their goals with less effort, less effort. time and fewer errors. Good usability helps to form, or maintain, a good image in front of users, and improves their experience during contact with the site (Palmerston [et al.], S.d.).

Conclusions

Today, the organization - and more specifically its Public Relations Department - will have to make it imperative to implement a business plan for this area. Operating in accordance with the overall strategy, it may cover a certain period of time, a particular event or series of events. The Public Relations Plan materializes in a document that structures the defining elements of this specific type of company communication, and its usual rubrics include different aspects (Marchiori, 2006; Wragg, 1992). All steps are important, but the process "begins with monitoring the social environment, which does not seem easily reached" (Broom, (2009 [1985]: 287). However, without this research, technicians only they can simply state that they know a particular situation and can recommend a solution, by conducting research and analysis, they are able to present and defend proposals based on facts and theories, assumptions about publics and public relations consequences. "(idem: 288). Its main objective is to reduce uncertainty in decision making. Although, of course, it cannot answer all questions or influence all decision making, methodical and systematic research underpins effective public relations programs. The inquiry process begins with listening, which requires constant effort, channels must be created and kept open. Failure to comply with this principle may lead to inappropriate communications about irrelevant subjects or to non-existent audiences. Other means of research should be considered, such as the existence of informants in key sectors of the organization and the surrounding environment, or more formal means, such as the analysis of secondary data, or the preparation and application of surveys, observing the scientific rules necessary for its reliability. In summary, we understand - following the above - that this social monitoring should be continuous, not assuming punctual or sporadic character. Then the problem or opportunity must be detected, a process that starts with the assumption that something is wrong or could be, or that it might be better. It is therefore necessary to describe in detail the dimensions of the problem, the factors that aggravate or mitigate it, and the audiences involved or affected by the situation.

In an immediate phase, it is essential to identify the important publics for the institution. This is because any organism would like to obtain the goodwill of all human groups that affect or are affected by it. However, and because resources and possibilities for public relations are limited, attention and efforts have to focus more heavily on some of them. "The need now is to apply constraints, and decide exactly which publics can be reached, and effectively reached,

within the limits of the budget, which is crucial information for the choice of media” (Jefkins, 1998 [1980]: 45). The main audiences of an institution are those that relate to it on an ongoing and active basis - employees, clients / users and the community (Oliveira & Paula, 2008; Stacks, 2002). These groups are related not only to the institution but also to each other in important ways: one can strongly influence the attitudes and behavior of others towards an organization. An example of this is the case of an institution where employees are satisfied with their activity and the way they take up human relations in the workplace; In family or social circles, the image conveyed in relation to the organization will assume greater credibility and notoriety.

At a later stage, it is possible to measure the attitudes of the relevant audiences. In fact, after identifying its various audiences, the institution needs to assess how each of them perceives it. Some information about the attitudes of each group can be obtained simply through regular contact with its members. However, impressions collected solely on the basis of informal contacts will not necessarily be reliable. An interesting way to work at this stage is the Focus Group discussion, with six to ten participants from a key audience, who will reveal their knowledge and feelings towards the institution. Of course, the remarks resulting from this type of initiative will not be fully representative, but can provide valuable insights and raise pertinent questions for the organization, which will try to explore them more systematically, for example through public opinion polls about its image.

The next moment to consider is targeting attitudes of the target audiences: through periodic opinion polls about their opinions, the institution collects consistent data on how it is perceived. These findings should be systematized and the parameters to be altered will meet specific and measurable criteria. Making the goals concrete facilitates the determination of the necessary activities, and provides a basis for evaluating the success of the Plan.

With all this data in mind, it will be possible to devise a strategy for dealing with the situation, or for capitalizing on the opportunity. This leads us to planning, materialized in strategic decisions and definition of working methods. Of course, the preparation of a plan inevitably does not lead to success, but it does increase the likelihood of success, as well as the development of cost-effective PR strategies. We know that often an institution has many options for trying to improve the attitudes of a specific audience; however, each project involves valuable time and money in contemporary societies. For this reason, the desired level of action improvement in each project should be calculated to arrive at the best set of cost / outcome measures.

The action and communication program designed to achieve the specific objectives for each of the publics leading to the achievement of the overall objective can now be implemented. It is therefore necessary to act and communicate: “Public Relations have matured into the role of helping organizations decide not only what to say but what to do” (Harold Burson, apud Cutlip [et al], 2001: 404). This includes changes to the institution's policies, procedures, products, services and behaviors. These changes seek to achieve organizational objectives while meeting the needs of their audiences; that is, they serve the mutual interests of the parties involved. In turn, effective communication makes a careful selection of the techniques and means to use. Segmentation is therefore a key idea, depending on the specificities of each target group, and program communication should be focused, targeted, and not inaccurately disseminated in all directions.

In a final stage, the Plan is completed with the evaluation of the results. If the implementation of the actions can be attributed to responsible technicians, who will know the concrete

objectives, time and budgets available, the Public Relations Department is responsible for supervising the efforts and controlling the results, for example by analyzing the space occupied by the news disclosed, according to the advertising table in force in each media (somewhat imperfect method, since news has more credibility than advertising). In addition to this type of assessment, content analysis may also be performed by classifying the news as positive, neutral or negative. The image of the organization can also be a constantly controlled aspect, through the opinion polls, being the constitution of panels of individuals to follow the evolution of the opinions about it. Of course, throughout this process, certain activities are perceived as expensive in relation to the advantages that can come from them, and for that reason they are eliminated. On the other hand, public relations objectives can be very ambitious at the outset, which will require them to be modified; further problems may arise, requiring resource redirection. As the actions are implemented and the results measured, the institution's positioning can be reevaluated, return to previous steps, and assume other attitudes towards its specific audiences. Thus, it can be said that the Public Relations Plan is continuously recycled. "As the benchmark model suggests, today's evaluation of program impact is tomorrow's baseline for the next program cycle." (Broom, (2009 [1985]: 392).

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Cite this article:

Matias, A. & Cardoso, L. (2019). Strategic Planning of Public relations - Reducing uncertainty in Decision making. *International Journal of Science and Business*, 3(6), 203-214. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3547481>

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